

Well-Oiled Academics Must Engage Students By Effectively Using All The Pillars In A Learning Management System

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 02, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Electronic communication, BlackboardTM, Assessments, Engagement</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5550470</p>	<p><i>A traditional learning management system can extend the boundaries of a classroom beyond the concrete walls of a university. This would enable student learning at anyplace or anytime where internet connectivity exists. However, a number of requirements would have to be met in order to achieve this, which includes a well-maintained learning management system and a well-oiled academic. A well-oiled academic refers to one whose teaching practice involves the active adoption of various educational technologies in order to promote student engagement. The purpose of this article is to present an objective measurement of student engagement with a module by considering their engagement with all four pillars of BlackboardTM that were adopted by an engineering academic. An ex-post facto study is employed along with descriptive statistics involving quantitative analysis of collected data for a 6-year period. Results indicate that students engaged with all four pillars of the learning management system during hours outside of classroom time. Two prominent pillars that were used by the students included Content (accessing and downloading notes and assignments) and Assessments (online self-reflective assessments and online assignment submissions). A significant correlation was not established between the four pillars and the final grades awarded to students at the end of the module. However, an average pass rate of more than 70% has been achieved by using this teaching approach as well as an extra average student engagement time of 17 hours per semester with the module. It is recommended that more academics adopt all four pillars of a learning management system in order to promote student engagement and further student learning outside of the classroom environment.</i></p>

Introduction

"I am enjoying my face changing, as well as realizing that at the same time, as you get older, the machine isn't as well-oiled as it was (Brainy Quote, 2020)." These words, by actress Kate Winslet, who played Rose DeWitt Bukater in the film Titanic, well illustrate that the human body may be seen as a well-oiled machine during one's youth. However, when one grows older, the well-oiled machine tends to degrade in performance as our vitality diminishes. A similar analogy may be applied to academics in higher education today.

It has been noted that technology will not replace teachers, but teachers who use technology will probably replace teachers who do not use it. Academics who therefore adopt educational technologies in their teaching practice are adapting to the ever-changing landscape of higher education. They are adapting to students who are 'digital natives', having grown up with technology and who are indeed technologically 'savvy'. Academics therefore who actively adopt various educational technologies are seeking to enhance student engagement and learning. This is based on the strongly held premise that technology can help students learn more effectively, which could lead to higher academic achievement (Chigona et al., 2014). These academics may well be termed 'well-oiled academics', as they have replaced their old oil (outdated traditional teaching methods) with new oil (complementing face-to-face teaching with educational technologies). "Oil changes" may be achieved by replacing teacher-centered approaches with learner-centered approaches, by supplanting surface learning with deep learning, and by trading the 'sage on the stage' with a 'guide on the side'. Just like a motor car's performance improves after a service (which includes an oil-change), so an academic's performance, and that of the students, may be enhanced by adopting various educational technologies in his or her teaching practice.

One such technology is a learning management system (LMS). The effective use of a LMS has been shown to enhance student support given by an academic (A.J. Swart, 2015), to promote student engagement with the course content (A.J. Swart, 2016a), to enable students to engage in reflective practice (A.J. Swart, 2016b), to help students attain academic success (A.J. Swart, 2017a, 2017b), and to assist students to negate the

Ebbinghaus 'forgetting curve' (A.J. Swart & Venter, 2018). Of all these benefits, student engagement stands out. Research by Kuh(2009) supports this as student engagement is defined as the time and effort students devote to activities linked to the desired outcomes of undergraduate education. Desired outcomes, or learning outcomes, are stipulated in each module and are at the center of student learning in higher education today (Lawrence Meda & Arthur James Swart, 2017). Not only do they form the basis for selecting various assessment strategies, but they have also been linked to graduate attributes. The International Engineering Alliance (IEA) stipulates 12 graduate attributes, that need to be embedded into any engineering curriculum, in response to current Industry needs (L. Meda & A.J. Swart, 2017). Therefore, when student engagement is enhanced, more time and effort is devoted to the achievement of learning outcomes, to the successful completion of assessments and to the demonstration of graduate attributes, thereby enabling a student to be better prepared for Industry.

Measuring student engagement is often suggested as a proxy for assessing the quality of education (Kuh, 2009), which is indicative of its critical role in educational outcomes. However, it is sometimes a difficult task to achieve (Liu et al., 2015). The research question therefore arises "What student engagement with a module can be objectively gauged, or measured, when considering the four pillars available in a LMS?"

The purpose of this article is to present an objective measurement of student engagement with a module by considering all four pillars of an institutional LMS that were adopted by an engineering academic in order to enhance student learning. The importance of student engagement is firstly given. The research context follows along with the methodology. Findings, interpretations and conclusions round off the article.

Student engagement and module credits

The term "student engagement", on its own, has some elements of ambiguity, as one does not clearly understand what type of engagement is required or to what extent it should occur. It can be a somewhat subjective process (Tucker, 2017) and a difficult task to measure (Liu et al., 2015). Astin(1984) defines it as "the amount of physical and psychological energy that the student devotes to the academic experience". Therefore, some measure student engagement by simply measuring the attendance of a student in class (Douglas & Alemanne, 2007) (this relates to physical energy), while other research aims to indirectly measure the cognitive and personal development of student college experiences (Pascarella et al., 2010) (this relates to psychological energy). It is therefore essential to define what student engagement means in this study, in order to have a coherent and consistent usage and understanding of the term. Student engagement is conceptualised as the time and effort that students spend in accessing all four pillars of a LMS, which may be directly linked to the credits and notional hours of a module.

It is fundamentally important to emphasise that although students can engage with content using a LMS, the presence of an instructor is indispensable as he/she is there to facilitate and guide the learning process (Meda, 2017). This resonates with the view of Bill Gates who articulates that, "Technology is just a tool. In terms of getting the kids working together and motivating them, the teacher is the most important." A teacher, lecturer or instructor creates a platform where meaningful student engagement takes place and he/she guides students learning to ensure that their experiences remain focused on the courses' objectives (Deo, 2016).

Facilitation of student engagement using a LMS is close to Vygotsky's (1978) social constructivist approach where students can interact with one another and get support and guidance from an instructor. This interaction can occur online or offline, as students can collaborate with each other in a LMS. An instructor who uses a LMS to engage students in all four pillars further applies the constructivist learning approach. This is applauded in higher education as it does not limit students to being mere knowledge receivers, but also becoming active knowledge producers (Meda, 2017).

The usage of a LMS can also enable an instructor to provide scaffolding for a student, as a student may receive multiple opportunities to construct, or reconstruct, knowledge through various online interactive and collaborative projects they are involved in (Lonn, 2009). Academics therefore have a big responsibility of ensuring that a LMS enhances students' learning experiences by using all four pillars, and not just one or two of them. Otherwise, it may be reduced to a content "dumping site" where only content and administration are used while communication and assessment are ignored (Carman & Haefner, 2002).

It must be noted that simply measuring student accesses to a LMS cannot be equated to student engagement. It is possible that a student can login to a LMS for a long period of time without actually doing anything constructive. Mwalumbwe and Mtebe(2017) argue that a combination of time spent on a LMS, the number of

downloads a student makes and the frequency of logging in have no significant impact on student learning performance. Similarly, Ping (2011) contends that if a LMS is judged purely by the amount of time students spend on the site, while downloading or navigating across different sites, then a LMS would be a content “dumping site”. However, if a LMS is judged by a student’s use of all four its pillars, then one can safely argue that engagement is taking place. This is due to the fact that the student will be collaborating with other students in the course, access learning materials uploaded by the instructor and other peers, participating in assessment tasks and obtain announcements about the course (Schutte et al., 2016).

A LMS has the potential of enhancing student engagement and learning as it allows students to spend time on the platform interacting with others and with the course content (Rambe, 2017). This collaboration can occur when completing online assessments / assignments or through discussion forums. A LMS is ideal to use to facilitate different learning experiences. This resembles with Isaias and Issa’s (2013) view that the benefits of using a LMS in the digital era is innumerable as it results in a win–win situation in different higher education contexts.

In the context of Saudi Arabia where a LMS was recently introduced, Hussein (2011) postulates that a LMS has brought significant changes to universities, as students now enjoy transformative collaborative learning experiences. Similarly, Pusuluri, Mahasneh and Alsayer(2017) contend that in Saudi Arabia, university students were satisfied with the collaborative and interactive nature of a LMS, as it offered a lively and interesting learning environment with a variety of learning experiences.

In Portugal, university students applauded the use of a LMS mainly due to the various engagement activities, describing the learning platform as sustainable and interesting (Isaias & Issa, 2013). This corresponds with the way the platform is conceptualised in South Africa, where it is believed to be a solid student engagement tool upon which effective teaching and learning rest (Schutte et al., 2016). The use of a LMS is encouraged in South African universities, as it increases student interest and involvement with the course or module. Thus, academics are striving to widen their horizons by using all four pillars of a LMS in order to create interactive experiences for students to enhance their learning (A.J. Swart, 2016a). Key disadvantages do exist and relate to a combination of technical matters, such as system downtime, poor internet connectivity on campus and the cost of buying Internet data bundles (Meda, 2017).

A final key reason for effectively using all pillars in a LMS is highlighted by the recent global COVID-19 pandemic. Institutions around the globe were forced to suspend face-to-face classes and move all teaching online as part of “emergency remote teaching”. This has been defined as a “temporary shift of instructional delivery to an alternative delivery mode due to crisis circumstances” (Hodges et al., 2020). Although various forms of educational technology were used to keep students engaged (such as WhatsApp), many institutions mandated their staff to make effective use of their LMS, including the Central University of Technology (CUT) in South Africa.

In the South African context, a one-year long qualification has a minimum of 120 credits which equates to 1200 notional hours. A 3-year qualification would require a minimum of 360 credits that equates to 3600 notional hours. These notional hours would comprise a number of activities, such as the time a student spends attending class, completing venue-based assessments, working in a laboratory, reviewing notes at the end of a day, preparing for an assignment, etc. Objectively measuring some of these activities is not difficult. For example, a 3 hour venue based assessment is an objective measurement. However, measuring the time a student takes to prepare for an assignment is more of a subjective process. Increasing the number of objective measurements is preferred, as this provides more concrete evidence that a student has attained the required notional hours, and thus credits, of a given module.

One objective measurement that can contribute to this concrete evidence involves measuring the engagement of students with all four pillars of a LMS. The authors re-iterate that this does not solely imply simply measuring the accesses and downloads of content material. No, student engagement with all four pillars needs to be used within a LMS to make this measurement objective and meaningful. These four pillars are:

- Content – This focuses mainly on the information which academics upload onto the platform for students to access, either in an interactive way or simply for downloading. Some of the content includes study guides (detailing the learning outcomes), assignment templates, prescribed reading material, exam preparation documents and power point presentations.

- Administration – This is mainly used by instructors to manage the module, and includes the calendar and grade centre. The calendar reminds students of deadlines while the grade centre helps students keep track of their academic results and to monitor the improvement in their course grades.
- Communication – This is where communication and interaction between students and instructors occur. It usually includes announcements and discussion forums.
- Assessment – This pillar focuses on various assessment strategies. It can include self and peer assessments along with practical assignments with predefined rubrics.

Engagement by students in accessing all these pillars in the BlackBoard™ LMS was determined for an electronic communication module at CUT in South Africa. This constitutes the research context of this study.

Research context

Electronic Communications 4 (EKM4) is an optional offering, or module, for the Baccalaureus Technologiae (BTech: Engineering: Electrical) qualification in South Africa (Central University of Technology, 2015). Students obtain 120 credits when they successfully complete this qualification. The majority of modules in this BTech programme have a credit value of 12, indicating that students should dedicate at least 120 notional hours to it (1 credit = 10 hours). A compulsory capstone module (termed Industrial Projects 4) is structured differently with 36 credits attached to it requiring a full year of work (often during the second year of study) (A.J. Swart & Toolo, 2015). CUT operates on a semester basis, of roughly 14 weeks, during which time BTech students would normally attend one classroom session per week (4 hours in duration) in which all theory and practical work for that given week was completed. Electrical engineering students need to be in possession of a National Diploma (minimum of three years to complete) before they can register for the BTech programme.

The syllabus of EKM4 is primarily aimed at telecommunication based students as it focuses mainly on digital transceiver systems. The learning outcomes incorporate illustrative verbs such as define, describe, sketch, analyze, calculate, design, determine and evaluate. The last five verbs are used extensively in the assessments as it places particular emphasis on the higher cognitive levels of learning listed in Blooms Taxonomy, which contribute to deep learning and critical thinking (A. J. Swart, 2010). This module further exposes students to a number of new fundamental theoretical principles that they have not encountered before, such as optic-fibre system design and power budgets

Research methodology

An ex-post facto study is employed along with descriptive statistics involving quantitative analysis of the collected data. An ex-post facto study is a type of non-experimental research in which the exploration of causal relationships is performed 'after the fact', meaning after variations of the independent variables of interest have already occurred (Polit & Beck, 2004). The independent variable of interest is the time students spent on the LMS (including the number of accesses) which may have an impact on the dependent variable of interest, namely student academic success. If the academic success is high, then it is assumed that the learning outcomes have been met and that student engagement with the course content was improved. Descriptive statistics, rather than inferential statistics, are used as the results are interpreted with regard to specific engineering students enrolled at CUT.

Quantitative analysis is important as it brings a methodical approach to the decision-making process, given that qualitative factors such as “gut feel” may make decisions biased and less than rational (Reddy et al., 2014). The target population was restricted to all engineering students enrolled for the module EKM4 between 2014 and 2019, thereby negating the use of a sampling technique. Final student grades for this module were also correlated (linear regression) to the time spent by the students in the LMS while engaging with the four main pillars.

The time and number of accesses were obtained by running specific available reports in the BlackBoard™ LMS. These reports include “All User Activity inside Content Areas”, “Course Activity Overview” and “Overall Summary of User Activity”. No ethical clearance was required as only student final grades and accesses to the LMS were used in the analysis. No personal information or opinions were obtained.

Results and Discussion

The majority of students were between 25 and 29 years of age, having already completed a National Diploma which requires a minimum of three years of full time study (maximum of five years). The average age of freshmen students entering the National Diploma is around 19 years of age, as they have just completed their

high school career (average age for Grade 12 learners in South Africa is 18 years (Kruger & Sonono, 2016)). The minority of students were female, which is one of the reasons why a global drive exists to encourage more women in engineering (Basart et al., 2015). The predominant home language was Sesotho, which is indicative of the Free State province in South Africa (A.J. Swart, 2014) where CUT is located.

Figure. 1 shows the four main pillars that exist within the BlackBoard™ LMS, along with the number of accesses to these by the students over the 6-year period. Clearly, the Content pillar (course material, notes and assignment templates) features predominately with 13486 accesses. However, if the LMS was used solely as a content “dumping site” (content repository for syllabi (White & Larusson, 2010), for handouts (Cosgrave & Bairre, 2010) and for traditional assignments (Daniels, 2009)), then there would be no assessment (Assess), Admin (Administration) or Comms (Communication) accesses. This is not the case, as Assess represents 26% of all accesses (6104 divide by the total number of accesses).

Figure. 1. Number of accesses to the four pillars within the LMS

The academic, in this module, has sought to use all four pillars of the LMS to promote student engagement with the course content outside of the classroom environment. He has tried to realize the true potential of LMS, which many academics or students have not yet achieved (2013). When considering the ratio of the four pillars, it seems that each subsequent pillar is accessed about 50% less than the previous one. This suggests a ratio of 2:1 between Content and Assessment, and between Administration and Communication. This is also depicted in Figure. 2, where the accesses to the four pillars are portrayed in percentages of the total accesses.

Figure. 2. Access percentages for the four pillars in the LMS

Figure. 3 indicates the number of accesses to the LMS for each day of the week. For 2014 through 2018, the peak access day is Wednesday, while in 2019 it was Sunday. The official timetable of the university placed EKM4 on a Monday for 2014 through 2017. In 2015 and 2018, it was scheduled on Wednesday. This clearly indicates that the students accessed the four pillars of the LMS outside of the classroom time, and even outside of the scheduled day for the class. Their work schedules would also have impacted on their studies and access time to the LMS, as the majority of the students were working full-time. These results do suggest that students engaged with the LMS throughout the week, which would have increased the amount of time that they spent with the course content.

Figure 3. Average number of accesses per weekday per year

Figure 4 illustrates the individual accesses to the four main pillars of the LMS over the 6-year period. The Introduction and Announcement tools of the LMS are classified under the Communication pillar (Swart, 2016a), as this is where regular updated instructions are conveyed to the students, which may also be sent to their individual email addresses.

Figure 4. Analysis of student accesses per year for communication, administration, assessments and content

The Grade Centre tool falls under the Administration pillar, as this is where the student's grades are recorded, along with the course mark calculations. Students need to obtain a minimum of 40% for their course mark to gain entry into the final examination. This tool would therefore be used by students right after an assessment or assignment has been graded by the academic, in order for them to track their progress through the semester.

The Practical assignment and Online assessment tools are considered under the Assessment pillar, as this involves self-reflective assessments and online assignment submissions. This would require students to engage with reflective practice as they would be given multiple attempts to complete an assessment based on immediate feedback that the system would provide to them. They would also need to demonstrate key graduate attributes, such as innovation and problem solving, technological literacy, numeracy and technical and conceptual competence in completing the practical assignments.

The Study Guide and Unit information tools (course notes in PDF format, abbreviated PPT slides from the classroom presentations and further worked-out examples) are classified under the Content pillar, and would be regularly accessed throughout the semester. Each Unit is made available at different times during the semester,

which would prevent the student from logging in and downloading all the course content during a single access session. No prescribed textbook is used, as the course content is drawn from recent freely available sources on the Internet (open-access journal articles and PDF notes of other academics in this field of study). This further enables the students to be exposed to a variety of authors and subject specialists, without the restriction of being limited to a singular textbook.

The Announcement tool had a larger number of accesses in 2018 and 2019, as compared to the other calendar years. This suggests that the academic started posting more announcements for the students to access, communicating more with them outside of the classroom environment.

Accesses to the Practical assignments were not high in 2014, as hardcopy assignments were still being used by the academic. This required students to print out their assignments and physically hand them into the academic on a specific day. However, from 2015 onwards, the Assignment tool in the LMS was initiated, requiring no more printouts as the students could complete the MSWORD template on their personal computer and upload it to the LMS at any-time before the due date. This also explains why the accesses to the Grade Centre and Reflections tools were low in 2014.

Student accesses to Unit 3 in 2014 were unusually high, as compared to the other units and calendar years. All units had a similar number of PDF notes which the students had to download, which would not have impacted on the number of accesses for the different units. This may suggest that students downloaded the PDF notes multiple times, without saving it on their personal computer.

Figure. 5 displays the results of the linear regression between the number of hours spent on the LMS and the final grades of the students. The highest number of hours for one student was 55 hours (far right) with the lowest being 3 hours (left). No significant statistical correlation exists. However, an average extra student engagement time with the module was objectively measured to be 17 hours (number of hours per student divided by the total number of students), while an average pass rate of 70% has been maintained for the past 6 years using this teaching approach (see Figure 6).

Figure. 5. Correlation between student final grades and the number of hours spent on the LMS

Figure. 6. Enrollments versus the examination pass rate

Conclusions

The purpose of this article was to present an objective measurement of student engagement with a module by considering all four pillars of an institutional LMS that were adopted by an engineering academic to enhance student engagement and learning. In order to maximize the benefits of a LMS for all stakeholders, all four pillars need to be used, but not necessarily in equal measure. Academics must continue to use a LMS to upload content for their students, but student time spent on this Content pillar should not exceed 60% of the total time in the LMS. Other pillars, such as Assessment (approximately 30% of the time spent in the LMS), Administration and Communication (remaining 10% of the total time spent in the LMS) must be used to scaffold student learning and assess the degree to which each student is achieving the learning outcomes of a module. This translates to a ratio of 2:1 when considering Content and Assessment, with both being critical to student learning. However, there is no correlation between the number of hours students spent in the LMS and the final grades that they obtained. However, the average pass rate of 70% is higher than the pass rate recorded in years prior to 2014.

It is erroneous to conclude that students are learning effectively with a LMS when one solely considers the amount of time they spend logged into the system without actually doing anything constructive. A true reflection of the usage and effectiveness of a LMS should be evaluated through student usage of all four pillars, and especially the assessment pillar. The reason for this relates to the time limit imposed on each online assessment which translates into the actual time a student spends doing something actively. In this study, the average time limit given to each online assessment was 35 minutes. This means that the student had to start the assessment and finish it within 35 minutes, or the system would automatically log the student out of the assessment. Having a number of online self-assessments would help improve the objective measurement of student engagement that does contribute to the notional hours and credits of a module.

Academics need to be well-oiled in order to effectively engage students by using different educational technologies, including a LMS. An average student engagement time with the module was objectively measured to be 17 hours, which contributes almost 15% to the required 120 notional hours that students must spend in this 12-credit module. This objective measurement may be used as evidence for accreditation purposes linked to the IEA, thereby proving that students are devoting time to a specific module. It is recommended to create awareness among more academics about the ratio that should exist between Content and Assessment in order to maximize the benefits that students may derive from using a LMS. This may also help erode the current perception among many academics that a LMS is simply a content “dumping site”, as they come to realize the full potential of using all four pillars in a LMS in varying degrees.

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